

EOSC & Research Infrastructures Opportunities and Strategies

Policy Workshop - Highlights Report

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PREPARED BY:
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ESFRI STRATEGIC ROLE AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This document highlights the key points that emerged from the Policy Workshop on 'EOSC and Research Infrastructures: Opportunities and Strategies' organized by the ESFRI-EOSC Task Force on March 16-17, 2026, in Milano. The workshop addressed the critical issues in linking European Research Infrastructures (RIs) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

About 90 participants, from Research Infrastructure, EOSC nodes, EOSC-SB, EOSC-A and EC, discussed the progress of convergence between RIs and EOSC Federation highlighting success stories as well as weaknesses in the process. The following points are a synthesis of the main issues, progresses and criticalities emerged in the two-day workshop.

1. EOSC AS A SYSTEM OF SYSTEMS

Is it preferable to have full evidence of the granularity of EOSC, or to offer the users a seamless "platform" for digitally enhanced/AI enhanced research workflows? The following aspects need to be considered:

- The Community needs to know what EOSC is capable of providing throughout all stages of implementation.
- Visibility and monitoring of the services that are growing in number and quality.
- Visibility and monitoring of the platform, as it is taking shape.
- Developing EOSC requires federating resources.
- RIs who provide resources need visibility for their contribution and a "juste-retour" (i.e. fair return on investment or proportional benefit).

2. WHAT ARE THE EOSC RESOURCES?

Do we need a Landscape Analysis (LA) of digital resources, data and services, and at what level of granularity?

- An EOSC-LA would showcase the full potential of the federation within each research domain
- The LA would help EOSC thematic nodes to address a larger reality, i.e. larger user base, a wider ecosystem, and cross-disciplinary challenges.
- The LA would encompass resources that are not (or not yet) in a position to develop autonomously an EOSC-compliant service
- The LA would reveal the overall scale of European research data and the economic implications of their "long term preservation" for future reuse, independent of the rapid obsolescence of data analysis tools and AI algorithms.

3. FINANCIAL ISSUES

The sustainability of RIs's engagement in EOSC implies addressing:

3.1 The fundamentals (cost, value and funding streams):

- The fundamentals involve understanding value, cost, and sustainable funding streams.
- Value could be better estimated from the EOSC-LA using an agreed methodology and metrics.
- Cost must include network bandwidth, CPU/GPU, and storage usage, along with services and human resources for continuous upgrading and 24h/365d operation". Goals of usage in 3/5/10 years must be set and benchmarked.

3.2. Savings:

- Estimate savings from sharing most advanced solutions, reducing duplication of efforts.
- Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI), REANA¹, SoBigData², and other services whose cost of adaptation to a broad set of communities is potentially much lower than ex-novo creation in all different domains.
- Metadata technology:
 - to be domain-specific for thematic research
 - to be exploitable for transdisciplinary research
 - to be interpretable by next generation AI
 - to be offered as an "automatic service" at the data production point -by FAIR-design technology or by algorithm-based FAIRification of raw data and metadata.

3.3. Co-Funding:

- Synergy is needed between national, EC, and institutional funding, alongside contributions from RIs.
- All relevant stakeholders must conduct a cost -benefit analysis, e.g. at the national level and seize the opportunities in a timely manner, such as those presented by the HORIZON-INFRA-2026-01-EOSC-01 pilot³.

4. NEED TO BUILD A SIZEABLE USER COMMUNITY

EOSC is more than RI-data sharing and servicing, but the RIs are the most prepared and advanced data producers for implementing the EOSC data space.

¹ REANA - Reusable Analyses

² SoBigData.eu

³ EU Funding & Tenders Portal

RIs should integrate complementary (i.e. essential) and supplementary (extra) EOSC services directly into the RI services offered to their users, though their access portals and Virtual Research Environments (VREs).

The EOSC Handbook progresses very well, but the RIs have expressed a need for an EOSC-toolkit. This toolkit should facilitate onboarding services, by providing technical guidelines and showcasing best-practice examples to minimise technological hurdles and complexities. Nevertheless, the onboarding and enrolling process must address the following:

- Resource Allocation: cannot be performed pro-bono, i.e. they require dedicated support and funding
- Economic Framework: a Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) for RIs joining EOSC must be structured to provide a clear reference for securing national contributions and engagement
- Variable Geometry: should reintroduce and adapt the “variable geometry” concept that enables the ESFRI RI ecosystem to grow and manage about 26-30 B€ of “distributed investments” in the last 20+ years of European Strategic Roadmaps.

5. COMMUNITY AND STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

This third ESFRI-EOSC Task Force workshop, the most attended so far, saw the participation of numerous Research Infrastructures (RIs) that had not participated in the 2024 workshops (FAIR-data productivity in January 2024 and Prototyping the EOSC Federation: Nodes And Linkages in November 2024), and are not yet involved in onboarding or node creation processes. The expanded and diverse audience brought new elements to the discussion, revealing significant differences in how EOSC is perceived today. It was evident that RIs not yet involved in the Federation buildup are often unaware of the Federation's current state-of-the-art, open issues, and of the active working groups. For many RIs in the research community, EOSC still appears “cloudy”, “confusing” in the practical returns, and “poorly organised” - an image that does not reflect the actual progress made in the last year. In contrast to the uncertainty of newcomers, RIs already engaged in the EOSC Federation process provided significantly more encouraging interventions and mature analyses, highlighting the need for better communication and strategic engagement to bridge the gap and scale up buildup activities across the ESFRI RI landscape.

6. TAKE-AWAY POINTS FROM THE WORKSHOP FOR THE WAY FORWARD

The workshop underlined a number of findings that have to be addressed in the buildup of the EOSC Federation and of the EOSC ecosystem as a whole:

- Building the Federation is a process and we are still in the early phase, with the services and data of the first 13 nodes becoming publicly available to European researchers in autumn 2026.

- those RIs participating in the Federation, report benefits for them already before the start of the operational phase through gain of expertise in connecting data and services, engagement in new collaborations, and additional ideas and opportunities becoming apparent.
- RIs not yet involved need to find clear instructions on how to create nodes or to enroll data and services into the Federation. This has to go beyond the EOSC Federation Handbook and should include cost-benefit analysis, tutorials, and tailored guidance in the process.
- The Commission is highly committed to EOSC and to the Federation, providing substantial support through the FP9 work programme and supporting the definition of a strong, sustainable model for EOSC under FP10.
- Member states and associated countries understand the need for persistent support of the operational phase of the Federation. Although this support varies from country to country, a common effort is envisioned to provide more coherent and sustainable support by Member States and Associated Countries to the EOSC Federation under FP10.
- Collaborative events, such as the ESFRI-EOSC Workshop in March 2026, are an excellent tool to continue and to deepen the communication between the RIs and the partners involved in EOSC and to tackle the challenges ahead.

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